

STUDY OF CONSTRUCTION DEFECTS WITH STRUCTURAL FORENSIC ANALYSIS OF BUILDING-A Review

Rekha Shinde¹ and Dr.Bikram Prasad²

¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, SVITS, SVVV Indore

² Associate Professor, Oriental University Indore

ABSTRACT

Failures in buildings are the common phenomena. Negative impacts in the quality of construction may led to loss of resources of the project. The poor construction along with improper material handling may led to failures and defects in construction, which can cause unnecessary loss of resources of the project such as time, money etc., Furthermore, if the failures are left untreated, it will lead to more serious problems such as damages to the life along with capital. Therefore, the study is aimed to identify contribution factors which led to defect and failures of building. This study is further more about identifying the common contributing factors of the structural failures in construction project. The Study of Forensic Investigation details of the failure of the construction will provide many outlines to construction professionals for learning from past failures so that such failures could be minimize. "Forensic Engineering is the study of materials, products, structures or components that fail or does not operate or function as designed, causing damage to property. The forensic investigation is very useful to develop practices and procedures to reduce failures of the building elements. It also provides guidelines for conducting failure investigation". This study will investigate the basic factor which led to the cause of the failure of a structurally damaged building. This Investigation also investigates elements of building for the strength & life of an existing building. The study examines the effect of the quality of material along with workmanship and concrete production, supervisor & also for the check for analysis & designing.

Keywords - Structural Defect & Failure, Structure Forensic Engineering, Forensic Tests, Material test, Design and analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

In present scenario world of fast rising era where the thing of the future boils down to a country's ability to establish world class infrastructures. The construction professionals, builders, architects, engineers consider the structural stability as the most important aspect of the project. Recently, it has been noticed that the present problems faced by the professionals is building failure & its collapse. To understand the factors behind the failure and collapse, we need to study forensic engineering and investigation study, which is very necessary to analyze the failure of structure. Forensic engineering is the investigation of failures of buildings and structures which are the consequences of serviceability to catastrophic and this serviceability may lead to legal activity, including both, civil & criminal. Therefore forensic engineering includes the investigation of the materials, machineries, workmanship, products, structures or function as designed, causing personal injury, damage to economic loss and personal loss. The consequences of such failure and defects in building may led to action under either criminal or civil law together. Generally, the purpose of a forensic engineering and investigations is to locate the causes of failure along with a view to get better performance of the asset. It can also include examination for property claims, especially insurances and patents.

2. FORENSIC ENGINEERING IN TREND

In some countries, Forensic structural engineering has become is evolving into a designated field of professional practitioners so that they can determine the causes of structural failures and identifying the parties responsible. The practice of forensic engineering involves engineering investigations and rendering problems along with giving expert testimony in judicial proceedings. Whether the failure in building occur during construction or defect is not treated during their service lives, failures of construction facilities and structures are almost followed by engineering investigations and resolution of claims. As the findings, compulsory create claims of damage and often result in disputes and legal entanglements. The forensic structural engineer operates in an adversarial environment and needs not only be able to perform the necessary investigations but also to have an understanding of the ins and outs of the practice of forensic engineering—which this paper intends to enhance.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Robert T. Ratayet et [2018] This paper consists an overview of the professional practice of forensic structural engineering. Forensic Engineering mainly includes the discussions of structural failures along with origins of failures and types of cases of failures, causes of failures, the standard of care for design, importance of codes and standards. The duties of professionals

and constructors are to perform the brief outline of the process of forensic investigation, along with references to detailed publications, meaning and importance of “reasonable degree of engineering certainty,” forms of dispute resolutions, who is an expert consultant and what the role of an expert consultant are along with a brief look about how the practices differ in various countries.

Kimball J. et al [2018] This paper discusses how a building failure investigation may be influenced by first impression myopia and provides strategies to guard against its detrimental effects. Case studies that demonstrate examples of first impression myopia pitfalls are presented. Overcoming the consequences of first impression myopia requires objective critical reviews by an independent qualified reviewer during the investigation. Periodic reassessment of investigation objectives, including rejection and replacement of the chosen failure hypothesis, is also required.

Thamilarasu V. et al, [2017] The purpose of the study is to check the effectiveness of the quality work in view of improving quality, safety & reduction in wastage of resources in a construction project. The Paper reviews about the implementation of quality analyses of the perspective of employees and workmen regarding quality of workmanship in construction process. This paper reports a case study of a residential building constructions of located in India and analyzing the extent of quality workmanship achieved. Firstly, Improper compaction and honeycomb issues and secondly, handling of materials and safety measures are found to be degrading the effectiveness of workmanship involved. The defects are documented and the causes for that particular problem are analyzed upon. The study had provided that the suitable remedial measures for rectifying the defects occurred within the structure which acts as a tool in the execution for the corrections as soon as possible.

Olawale et al August, [2015] In the study it had been found that building collapse has become a very common occurrence in Nigeria. During the study, relevant analysis cum investigations carried out on a collapsed building along with Osun State University, Osogbo which includes 1) site reconnaissance survey, 2) soil testing and particle size distribution test and 3) non-destructive test of the remaining debris of the structural elements of the collapsed building. The results of the study showed that the building was designed under critical areas of the building elements. The investigation also revealed that the client did not employ any qualified Professional to provide detailed working drawing and through proper supervision of construction which contributed majorly to the collapse of the building. It was concluded that lack of detailed working drawings along with supervision and use of inappropriate material including poor concrete production and improper reinforcement placement among others, contributed to the collapse of the building .

Yogen Ogunbiyi et al, Dec. [2015] The study was carried out to investigate the remote causes which leads to the collapse of a three-Storey Building in the particular area of Ile-Ife. The study analyzes the original design of the structure submitted for approval and construction and the

researchers further re-designed the Structural elements which were required for the stability of the building. The building under consideration was under-designed. Also the contractor did a shoddy work along with using inappropriate materials in the construction of the building.

Jonathan G M Wood et [2015] The study had shown that the information collected from rigorous investigations of performance failures of construction can be applied to reduce risks and also to improve construction standards for practicing professional engineers, within design and contracting organizations, and nationally and internationally in developing improved standards and guidance.

Kenneth L. Carper et [2015] Design and Construction Failures is a compilation of case studies from the files of one of the nation's leading forensic investigators. Numerous structural failures are presented involving a wide variety of constructed facilities, including buildings, bridges, and waterfront structures. Separate chapters discuss failures of concrete, steel, and masonry structures; foundation problems; and corrosion. The book concludes with a discussion of forensic practice.

Jackson Musyoka Kioko et [2014] The study is about the various causes of building failure in Kenya. The study reveals that along with various causes that lead to collapse of buildings, lack of African code of practice was one of the major factor that was put in consideration in the study. In African countries, mostly codes of practice used were foreign codes either from Britain or Indian codes.

Krishnamurthy,Dr.Natarajan et [2007] The Study was about the importance of forensic engineering, which is the light of the increased need in the construction industry. Proper documentation of the design and construction process along with discussions are to be prepared and then the failure investigation should point out critical procedures and protocols investigation. The study illustrates the application of a few classical case studies from around the world.

Kumalasari Wardhana et al [2003] In this Study, a 225 building failures were recorded in the United States from 1989 to 2000. The result showed that 63% of all cases was the failures of low-rise buildings, followed by multistory buildings as a distant second. the most frequent to fail were the apartments. The most frequent principal caused identified were external events, construction and maintenance deficiencies. External events include vehicular impact and collision rain, wind, snow. Construction deficiencies identified were unsafe excavation operations, improper renovation, unplanned demolition, poor workmanship, maintenance deficiencies are associated with building which deteriorates the basic strength of building, that was overlooked and improperly maintained. A comparative analysis conducted between this study and two previous studies indicates an inclined trend of relative failure occurrences of low-rise and multistory buildings. The study also suggests that, despite the recent enhancement of information technology, current sources of information are still incomplete. The creation of new

complete databases, further improvement of information sources, and their dissemination through the Internet are deemed essential to prevent building failures from recurring.

4. CONCLUSION

*From the literature reviews, it is observed that failure in a structure occurs due to various reasons during the construction & they are responsible for the failures. As per the study while constructing the structures, testing of soil, sand & concrete should be taken.

*This study will prepare a structure forensic report of an existing structure & find out the errors in design, on the basis of test results of samples this study will identify the cause of failure & the strength of the structure & this study also provides the prevention from the failure.

*It has been clear from the previous papers, that this kind of study is done more in foreign countries. There is no awareness in India about this kind of study.

*This study is aimed to identify contribution factors to building defect and failures, which frequently occur in construction project in order to minimize time and cost involved.

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